

EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE OF HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS WITH REGARD TO TYPE OF SCHOOL – A STUDY

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ABSTRACT The present study investigated the emotional intelligence of higher secondary students with respect to type of school. The investigator used survey method of research to study the emotional intelligence of higher secondary students with respect to type of school. The study was conducted on 300 higher secondary students by giving due representation to government school, government aided and self-financed schools of Sivagiri Taluk. The investigator used simple random sampling technique. The emotional intelligence scale constructed by V. Kasirajan (2015) was employed. The descriptive analysis of data was done by finding out the level of emotional intelligence of higher secondary students with respect to type of school and the “F” value was calculated to the significant difference. From the result of the one way ANOVA, the investigator found that there is significant difference in emotional intelligence of higher secondary students with respect to type of school.

KEYWORDS : Emotional Intelligence, Higher Secondary Students, Type of School, ANOVA, Scheffe test

INTRODUCTION

The term “emotional intelligence” was introduced in 1990 by two American University professors Dr. John Mayer and Dr. Peter Salovey in their attempt to develop a scientific measure for knowing the differences in people’s ability in the areas of emotions. However, the credit for popularizing the concept of emotional intelligence goes to another American psychologist Daniel Goleman (1995). Emotional Intelligence is the product of one’s heredity and its interaction with his environmental forces. According to S. Hein, “The innate potential to feel, use, communicates, recognize, remember, learn from, manage and understand emotions.” According to Lea Brovedani, “Being able to recognize, name and appropriately deal with emotions that we feel and experience. We may all feel anger, emotional intelligence I knowing what to do with the emotion of anger to achieve the best possible outcome.”

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Emotional intelligence is different from general or common intelligence. It’s the ability of an individual to monitor their own emotions, to monitor the emotions of others, to understand the differences between them, and to use all of this information in order to guide their actions. This is about accurately understanding the emotions of oneself and others, as well as expressing emotions in a way that’s accessible. A high level of emotional intelligence is an essential aspect of learning. The ability to develop the skill of emotional understanding is a driver not only in the realm of relationships but also in the realm of education. The ability to manage emotions is essential for classroom success, where students must learn how to interact reasonably within the academic environment while focusing on learning. Students with low emotional control react in a negative toward proposed changes, as they are not equipped to deal effectively with emotionally stressful events, like testing or projects. On the other hand, students who are able to effectively manage their emotions tend to be optimistic and to take the initiative, reframing their understanding of stressful events as exciting. The ability to understand other people’s emotions, persuasions, motivation, conflict resolution mechanisms, and reasons for cooperation are probably the skills most essential for success in education and in the life that will come beyond the classroom. The positive reinforcement of an emotionally intelligent environment enhances the school environment, helping students to find not only academic success, but also life success outside of the classroom. With this background, the investigator wanted to study the emotional intelligence of higher secondary students with respect to type of school.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To find the level of emotional intelligence of higher secondary students with respect to type of school.
- To find out whether there is any significant difference in emotional intelligence of higher secondary students with respect to type of

school.

METHODOLOGY

The investigator used survey method of research to study the emotional intelligence of higher secondary students with respect to type of school.

POPULATION

The population of the present study are all the students studying standard XI and XII in higher secondary schools in Sivagiri Taluk.

SAMPLE

The study was conducted on 300 higher secondary students by giving due representation to government school, government aided and self-financed schools of Sivagiri Taluk. The investigator used simple random sampling technique.

TOOL USED

The emotional intelligence scale constructed by V. Kasirajan (2015) was employed.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUE USED

The descriptive analysis of data was done by finding out the level of emotional intelligence of higher secondary students with respect to type of school and the “F” value was calculated to the significant difference.

DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS OF DATA

To find the level of emotional intelligence of higher secondary students with respect to type of school.

Table - 1 Level of emotional intelligence of higher secondary students with respect to type of school

Variable	Type of School	Low		Average		High	
		Count	%	Count	%	Count	%
Emotional Intelligence	Govt.	20	21.3	65	69.1	9	9.6
	Govt. Aided	12	8.2	106	72.1	29	19.7
	Private	11	18.6	44	74.6	4	6.8

It is inferred from the above table that with regard to govt., 21.3% of students have low level, 69.1% of them have average level and 9.6% of them have high level of emotional intelligence. With regard to govt. aided, 8.2% of them have low level, 72.1% of them have average level, and 19.7% of them have high level of emotional intelligence. With regard to private, 18.6% of them have low level, 74.6% of them have average level, and 6.8% of them have high level of emotional intelligence.

INFERENTIAL ANALYSIS OF DATA

H0: 1 There is no significant difference in emotional intelligence of higher secondary students with respect to type of school.

6. Licensees of Pearson Education in South Asia.
<http://www.theedadvocate.org/4-dimensions-of-emotional-intelligence-for-students/>
 7. <http://www.connected.org/learn/school.html>

Table 1 F-test showing the significance difference in the emotional intelligence of higher secondary students with respect to type of school

Variable	Source of Variance	Sum of squares	df	Mean Square	Calculated F-value	Tabulated F-value	Remarks
Emotional Intelligence	Between groups	631.074	2	315.537	3.324	3.04	S
	Within groups	28189.7631	297	94.915			

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated 'F' value (3.324) is greater than the table value (3.04) for df (2,297) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. It shows that there is significant difference in emotional intelligence of higher secondary students with respect to type of school.

Table 2 Scheffe test showing the mean difference in the emotional intelligence of higher secondary students with respect to type of school

Government	Government Aided	Private	Result
115.56	117.29	-	*
115.56	-	118.87	-
-	117.29	118.87	-

*Significant difference at 5% level of significance

The Scheffe test shows that there is mean difference between government and government aided higher secondary students in their emotional intelligence. And also it clearly shows that the government aided higher secondary students have greater emotional intelligence than the government higher secondary students.

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

From the result of the descriptive analysis, the investigator found that more than 69% of higher secondary students have average level of emotional intelligence with regard to type of school. The reason may be due to fact that the higher secondary students are all in the stage of adolescent stage. From the result of the one way ANOVA, the investigator found that there is significant difference in emotional intelligence of higher secondary students with respect to type of school. And also from the result of Post Hoc test (Scheffe test), the investigator also found that the government aided higher secondary students have greater emotional intelligence than the government higher secondary students. So the investigator recommended that the government should insist all the schools to teach emotional skills at higher secondary level. Learning in school is a progressive, planned activity cast in the light of the firmly held belief that children are different from adults and that they need to be prepared for the adult world at the same time as they need to be protected from it. This conception of learning and the very idea of childhood are recent inventions. There are reasons to believe that, with the advent of an electronically networked society, the clear distinction between childhood and adulthood is disappearing. One thing is certain, whether it be via the media or directly in their lives, children are increasingly subjected to the whole range of emotions known to adults, not to mention a wide variety of relationships spreading from the best to the worst. Introducing emotions in schools would be a radical change! Yet schools do not change so readily. Those well-meaning people who have tried to introduce innovations in schools have come up against considerable resistance from teachers, students and parents alike. Yet without their active participation, no such far-reaching change is possible.

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